

Original Research Article

The effect of cultural values on the formation of the urban landscape of Yasouj

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Abstract

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This study was carried out aimed to investigate the effects of cultural values on urban landscape. To achieving this purpose, a researcher-made questionnaire has been designed based on the theoretical framework in which components of cultural values including relationships, forms and performances are developed in combination. Also, a mixed researcher-made questionnaire has been developed for measuring the urban landscape variable. The statistical population of this study is Yasuj. The effective components on the landscape, including human, natural, alive and absolute are analyzed and studied in order to analyze the urban landscape. The method used in this study is survey and a self-made questionnaire has been used to assess the components of the landscape and cultural values. Also, Anova's analysis method has been used to determine the relationship between landscape and cultural values. Simple non-probability sampling (also known as simple non-random sampling) was distributed among the citizens of Yasuj and data collection method was purposive. The questioner has implemented the questionnaire. The required data was collected and analyzed by SPSS22 software and the results were studied on two levels of descriptive and inferential statistics. In inferential statistics, Pearson correlation coefficient test was used for examination of the research hypotheses. In the present study, according to the results of the test of variance, there is a significant relationship between cultural values and urban landscape quality and it can be deduced that urban landscape will change with higher growth of cultural values.

Keywords: Landscape, landscape components, cultural values

INTRODUCTION

Urban development of the city of Yasuj is an emerging issue, which only has focused on construction of shelter for immigrants who constitute urban populations and nothing has been done to integrate cultural values in the urban landscape. Case study in this study is Yasuj in Iran where is located in the mountain range of Zagros Mountains and in the western south of Iran. One of the characteristics of this city is cold and mountainous climate with a slope of less than 20% from north to south. This city has a mountainous wilderness and oak forests with rainfall of over 750 mm per year (Portal of Iran meteorological organization 2015).

The present study is of utmost importance and necessity and its innovation aspects are related with this issue that the qualitative effect of cultural values in urban landscape design has been neglected. However, in the advanced countries in urban architecture aspect, it has observed that architectures with an effective urban landscape on citizenship culture has been designed and implemented. Human-made and collective constructions have a significant effect on citizenship culture and this kind of culture has brought requirements to human life in form of values and norms. According to Ashouri, culture is collective product of human beings, which can be

transferred and acquired, and is dynamic, flexible, reversible and influenced from the environment (Ashouri, 2001).

Values are of utmost importance because of two reasons: firstly they form the content of social norms, secondly they are the basis of our assessment of the phenomena around us, and in fact they can regulate human behavior in the realm of society (Gholizadeh, 2009). This study was carried out aimed to investigate the relationship between urban landscape and cultural values in the city of Yasuj and this study seeks to introduce cultural values. The architect of a building develops a special idea in his mind, and needs space to create space to be able to implement this idea, and it is the space that determines which wall of what kind of materials and colors appear in what part of the building space. Perhaps many people mistakenly think that the architectural space is enclosed by the walls, columns, and ceilings. If this perception is completely wrong, because as mentioned earlier, the nature of space determines that Which element should be placed where and social values have significant effect on these parameters in a positive or negative way, although this relationship can be two-way, that is, cultural values to be guided to create landscape architecture, or landscape to be guided o cultural values development, which these two variables and their effects are investigated in the present study. And the importance and necessity of this study is due to the need for needs assessment of the citizens of Yasuj based on the urban landscape approach and cultural values will be seriously damaged if the neglect of the urban landscape continues. The city of Yasouj has the necessary conditions for the formation of cultural values. The urban landscape is shaped based on both cultural and local conditions and urban regulations can't be effective alone in shaping a high quality urban landscape. Therefore, the present study seeks address the components of cultural values and urban landscape.

Theoretical framework and research background

Landscape

Janet believes that landscape as a discipline is defined as environmental, cultural, visual resources, metaphor of artistic image, ideology knowledge and effective factors on various relationships. Therefore, the landscape values assessment is usually performed in value categories using proposed criteria (aesthetic, historical, scientific, etc.) (Stephenson, 2008: 128).

Nowadays, the term "landscape" has found a comprehensive concept. Some scholars have considered it as a comprehensive definition of the natural environment, including all ecological characteristics, natural sciences, and physical properties of the earth and its conditions as well as the human-made environment.

Comprehensiveness the concept of landscape indicates the scope of other concepts related to the landscape, including landscape architecture, because its wide range includes all aspects of the natural environment to human-made environments, as well as it has shown all human-made activities to change the environment during human life.

Charles Waldheim has defined landscape architecture as an intermediate design discipline, which works in spaces between buildings, infrastructure and natural ecology system (Shane, 2003). According to Brunovsk, "Man is a unique creature and has talents that distinguish him from other animals." For this reason, he is not only a body in the environment and landscape contrary to them, but shapes the environment and the landscape. He explores nature with body and soul (John L. 2000). Michael Laurie has defined landscape architecture based on Girth ECKBO theory, "the art of designing, planning, and managing land, organizing the nature and human-made elements in which the acceptance of science and culture is revealed as knowledge in which maintaining natural resources and monitoring is of utmost importance and they are necessary to have an useful and enjoyable environment ("Laurie, 1986: 10).

Girth ECKBO defines landscape architecture from this perspective that it exists beyond buildings, roads, or urban facilities and is designed and developed by human beings, and is considered as merely an environment for human life and don't include forests and farm. This definition emphasizes the qualitative and quantitative relationship between landscape space and human. The definition provided by "ECKBO" is also consistent with the concepts mentioned by others. So that some scholars define landscape architecture as an extension of architecture with other tools and materials, in fact, both of them pursue a common goal. However, landscape architecture in many topics, in particular is close to some concepts, such as the concepts related to the creation and organization of space and space, but its field of activity is extensive and is typically related to the creation, organization, and management of open spaces of processes and artifacts.

In the concept of the landscape, expansiveness and comprehensiveness indicates the extent of other concepts related to the landscape, such as landscape architecture, because it can show its wide range from natural environment to human-made environments, as well as all its activities for changing the environment throughout human life. "The atmosphere of any place corresponds to an integrated form and spatial integrity, and each element individually in this place can be described and recognized with the help of this totality" (Schultz, 2008, 43).

Joseph Mallord William Turner RA, in his book entitled "City, like the landscape", defines the term landscape as follows: According to the history of spatial and syntactic science, it is reasonable that the term "landscape" can be

used as a term with a concept of a certain vision of the world.

The geographical location of the people determines the physical aspect of the landscape. Landscape psychology aspect is defined as mental structures, so that sense is interpreted through them. Turner, T. 1996.117.

Simon Bell (Simon Bell is a forester and landscape architect, Senior Research Fellow at Edinburgh College of Art, Associate Director of the OPENspace Research Centre and an associate professor at the Estonian University of life Sciences) believes; quality and capacity can be determined by landscape features assessment. And in this case, landscape assessment is done by looking at the dimensions of the landscape.

According to Seifoddini, that landscaping can be defined as "Any activity that changes the evident features of an area of land" (Seifoddini, 2012, 6). Landscape elements include the following four:

Living elements

Including ground vegetation cover, animals, or what is called the farming, this is the art of growing plants to create a beautiful environment within the landscape.

Natural elements

Forms of land surface, plains forms, highlands and water forms.

Human factors

Structures, buildings, fences or other material objects that have been created and installed by humans.

Absolute elements

Weather and light conditions.

Cultural values

The concept of "value" can be considered as an intrinsic and universal state, but now, in general, it is considered as a social structure due to cultural conditions of a time and place (Avrami et al., 2000). Browne et al during a study concluded that people have certain "values", but also "value" is expressed by them for certain objects. In this sense, understanding how to evaluate a landscape involves understanding the nature of the valuable object (or landscape aspect) and the nature of the value expressed to that object. These values can't speak: they

are only recognized when they are expressed by those who are part of the cultural field or those who are in a position where can observe and understand them (Stephenson, 2008: 129). Cultural values refer to those values that are shared by a group or community or are legitimized using an acceptable social method for valuation. Therefore, there are different methods for the landscape assessment due to different groups of values. A group of values are shared by those who are affiliated with a group, as well as another group is assigned by relevant experts. In this study, cultural values not only include features which are considered as part of "culture" such as stories and fairy tales traditionally, but also features that may be part of "nature", although they are valuable culturally" (Peart, 2004).

Carl Sauer and Berkeley School evolved the concept of "cultural landscape" in the mid-twentieth century, this concept revealed the emerging benefits of landscape human components. Carl Sauer sought to understand the role of people in the evolution of landscapes using methods such as morphological analysis and cultural history using an empirical approach (Leighly, 1963). The preservation of cultural diversity and biodiversity as a shared field of landscape is needed for increasingly awareness, as can be observed, for example, the comprehensive approaches identify and protect the landscape in the world heritage convention (UNESCO, 2002) and interest in sustainable natural and cultural relationships under the protected landscape approach, can be arisen in this regard (Brown et al., 2005).

There is relationship between individual identity (In philosophy, the matter of personal identity deals with such questions as, "What makes it true that a person at one time is the same thing as a person at another time?" or "What kinds of things are we persons?" Generally, personal identity is the unique numerical identity of a person in the course of time.) and group identity (Group identity refers to a person's sense of belonging to a particular group.) events and historical events which are associated with the perceptible environment. Therefore, culture and identity are not only about social communications but also have a strong relationship with space. Landscape development in an inappropriate way can alter or eliminate local and cultural distinctive features meanings, and create gaps between communities and past. In 2005, Antrop et al show that "culture in the sense of anthropology can be used as the entire lifestyle of a person; as a useful tool for giving identity to a group and referring to specific social processes". Cultural values refer to the growing values which are shared by a community or legitimized using an acceptable social method for valuation (Stephenson, 2008: 129).

The model of definitive elements of the landscape is developed by Crumley and Marcant (1990) this model suggests that the landscape is created by physical structures (things that are relatively independent of

Table 1. The following components are used to design cultural values questionnaire and they are evaluated using SPSS test (Source : Author)

	Components	Definitions (Questions are indirectly designed for cultural values based on Janet Stewson's Theory	Test method
16 questions about cultural values	Relationships Question 1 to 5	Sense of place, vitality, symbols of ideology and satisfaction has been investigated.	Test of research hypotheses by Pearson correlation method SPSS
	Forms : Question 6 to10	Physical, structures, vegetation cover, natural form and shape have been investigated.	
	Place Attachment Question 11 to 16	Traditional and human activities, environmental and natural processes, nostalgia have been investigated.	

human control such as weather, topography, geology) and social-historical structures (such as the social level, inheritance, communications, trade, laws). The landscape can be determined by these structures and their interpretations (aesthetics, symbolism, religious, ideological) (Stephenson, 2008: 130).

These concepts and models could provide the intellectual framework in which the cultural values model was developed, while the present study has focused on developing a model of cultural values in landscapes, especially given the growing emphasis on the landscape as "both the region and the role of human perception in the definition of that region," it was important that such a model be compatible with contemporary theories in terms of its landscape (Olwig, 2005, p. 294). Cultural values include not only features that are considered as "cultural" features traditionally (such as stories and fairy tales), but also have natural features that are valuable in terms of culture (Stephenson, 2008: 134).

Research

The necessity of research

The present study is of utmost importance and necessity and its innovation aspects are related with this issue that the qualitative effect of cultural values in urban landscape design has been neglected. However, in the advanced countries in urban architecture aspect, it has observed that architectures with an effective urban landscape on citizenship culture has been designed and implemented.

Question

Can the Yasouj urban landscape, with its specific features, provide a suitable context for creating and improving the cultural values of citizens?

Objective

Impact of cultural values on the landscape promotion approach.

Ideal objectives

Creating an attractive and applied landscape to increase the audience's attraction and ultimately create cultural values in the city of Yasouj.

The overall objective

Having effecton the cultural values and creating a sense of partnership with designing a unique landscape for Yasuj.

Variables

In the present study, dependent variable is landscape (effective components in landscape; Table 1) and the independent variable is cultural values (effective variables in cultural values; Table 2).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Combined research method

Research hypothesis

There is a significant relationship between formation of cultural values of Yasuj and the quality of landscape design. This study is a survey research, and the research method is correlation that has addressed the relationship between variables and Pearson's analysis was used to predict factors effecting on cultural values, these factors

Table 2. The following components are used to design landscape elements questionnaire and they are evaluated using SPSS test (Source: Author)

Components	Definitions (Questions are indirectly designed for landscape elements based on Janet Stewson's Theory)	Test method
Landscape elements	Human elements Question 17 to 20	Structures, buildings, fences or other material objects that have been created and installed by humans.
	Natural elements Question 21 to 24	Forms of land surface, plains forms, highlands and water forms.
	Living elements Question 25 to 28	Including ground vegetation cover, animals, or what is called the farming, this is the art of growing plants to create a beautiful environment within the landscape.
	Absolute Elements Question 29 to 32	Such as weather and light conditions.
		Test of research hypotheses by Pearson correlation method SPSS

Table 3. Correlation coefficient of the hypothesis

Correlation the hypothesis	coefficient of	Urban landscape	Relationships	Forms	Performances
Urban Landscape	Pearson correlation	1	, 532 **	, 540 **	, 830 **
	Significance level	-	, 000	, 000	, 000
	Number		405		

include relationships, forms, and Place Attachment have been investigated and the elements of the landscape include human, natural, living, and absolute.

The survey method

This study was carried out aimed to investigate the was used in this study and the Anova analysis method was used to determine the relationship between landscape and cultural values. Simple non-probability sampling (also known as simple non-random sampling) was distributed among the citizens of Yasuj and data collection method was purposive. The questioner has implemented the questionnaire. The required data was collected and analyzed by SPSS22 software and the results were studied on two levels of descriptive and inferential statistics. In inferential statistics, Pearson correlation coefficient test was used for examination of the research hypotheses (Table 3).

Statistical population

The statistical population in the present study is citizens of Yasuj city.

Sampling method

The statistical sample was selected using random sampling and completed in the spring of 2016. A sample (questionnaire), 384 people were selected based on Morgan's table and a questionnaire was distributed randomly among individuals in these areas of the city. Spss22 software has been used for analysis and the results have been analyzed in two levels of descriptive and inferential statistics. This study is considered as a correlational research. Pearson correlation coefficient was used in inferential statistics and linear regression was used to examine the research hypotheses.

Dependent variable in this study is urban landscape elements and independent variable is cultural values and

Figure 1. The scoring of landscape elements

mediating variables including relationships, forms, and performances. The validity of the research tool is obtained through content validity, face validity by referring to the professors and receiving their comments on the indicators. Also, the reliability of the questionnaire was evaluated through the correlation of the items and the total reliability of this tool was evaluated. The total questionnaire includes 32 questions. The alpha Cronbach's statistic, which varies from zero to one, is reliability index for the items of the research tool. The alpha value varies from zero to one. As this value approaches zero, the suitability of the questions isn't verified and if it approaches 1, that means the questions are suitable, which in this study, the suitability of the questions are verified with high ratio (0.884).

FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

In the present study, since we seek to investigate the effect of the dependent variable (landscape) on the independent variable (cultural values) in hypotheses, therefore, in the first step, we will address inferential analysis by converting a case study from quantitative to qualitative. Most of the participants in the study were aged 30 and 35 and were women and had a bachelor's degree and resided in Yasuj for 11 to 15 years.

Data collection method is descriptive (library) and inferential (field). The statistical population is not homogeneous (male and female) and simple random sampling method is used. Purposive data collection method includes:

The research assessment tool was analyzed the results of the questionnaire in inferential manner using analysis of variance method.

Research findings

Inferential statistics (The results of the questionnaire)

In the present study, since we seek to investigate the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable hypotheses, therefore, regression has been used in order to investigate the hypothesis of the test. One-variable regression has been used, because there is an independent variable in each of the hypotheses.

Research hypotheses testing

There is a significant relationship between urban landscape with cultural value components including relationships, forms, and performance (Table 3). According to the results of regression are calculated based on the results of questionnaires. And Figure 1 shows the scores for the landscape elements.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

According to the results of the test of variance, there is a significant relationship with cultural values and landscape quality, but no positive relationship was observed in this

study, that is, landscape enhancement should be addressed in order to establish a relationship, also the options of cultural values including relationships, forms, and performances in the quantitative analytical results, which are presented in table 3, which is calculated by regression based on the results of the questionnaires. The strengths and weaknesses of the components in order to restore the landscape of Yasuj city should be addressed in order to prioritize, which solutions and suggestions can be presented in future studies. According to the results obtained from the Cultural Values Questionnaire, the forms have had the highest score and performances have had the lowest score. In the landscape section, the highest score is achieved by human-made elements and the lowest score is achieved by living elements. According to the results and findings, these cases can be used to solve and improve urban landscape problems.

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